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Functionalized Porous Materials for the Selective Adsorption of Pharmaceutical Pollutants from wastewater

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The persistence of pharmaceutical pollutants in aquatic environments poses an increasing threat to ecosystems and public health due to their bioactive nature and resistance to conventional wastewater treatment processes. To address this challenge, this study investigates the design and development of advanced functionalized porous materials for the selective adsorption of pharmaceutical contaminants (Valsartan, Diclofenac, and Iopramide) from wastewater, with a particular focus to biomass-derived carbon adsorbents functionalized with ionic liquids and deep eutectic solvents, engineered to enhance adsorption capacity, selectivity, and reusability. Laboratory-scale experiments will assess the materials' performance through adsorption isotherms and kinetic studies. The optimization of parameters such as pH and temperature is carried out to maximize efficiency, regeneration and reuse to further evaluate the long-term sustainability and economic feasibility of the proposed materials. By contributing with innovative, high-performance, and environmentally friendly adsorbents, this work aims to advance wastewater treatment technologies and support the transition toward zero-pollution objectives in line with European sustainability goals.

References

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